

Solubilities of Sodium Chloride and Ion-Solvent Interaction in Dimethyl Sulphoxide—Water Mixtures at 25°

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The solubility of sodium chloride is determined in DMSO-H₂O mixtures at 25°. Log *s* varies linearly with mole fraction of water with an abrupt change of slope at $x(\text{H}_2\text{O}) \approx 0.675$. This shows that the solubility follows two exponential laws, in the ranges $x(\text{H}_2\text{O})=0$ to $x(\text{H}_2\text{O})=0.675$ and $x(\text{H}_2\text{O})=0.675$ to $x(\text{H}_2\text{O})=1.0$. $S_{(0-0.675)} = A e^{bx}$ ($A=0.453$ and $b=3.578$); $S_{(0.675-1.0)} = A' e^{b'x}$ ($A'=0.0851$ and $b'=6.057$).

PHYSICOCHEMICAL studies in DMSO-H₂O mixtures have drawn attention recently¹. Even though viscosity and density data² are available, practically no work seems to have been done on the solubility of electrolytes in DMSO-H₂O mixtures. The solubility of NaCl has been measured in DMSO-H₂O mixtures at 25° and an attempt is made to correlate the solubilities with ion-solvent interaction.

Materials and Methods :

DMSO (B.D.H) was purified as described earlier³. Analar NaCl was recrystallised from conductivity water and dried in Vac. at 110° for several hours. Purity was determined gravimetrically. (99.98±0.01%). All mixtures of DMSO and water were prepared by weight. Pure DMSO was handled in a dry box in an atmosphere of pure dry N₂. Saturated solutions were prepared by shaking excess of NaCl with the mixtures in stoppered bottles at 35° keeping them in a thermostat maintained at 25°±.01° for several hours. Solutions were analysed gravimetrically. Solubility was calculated as weight of NaCl in 100 g of the mixture.

Results and Discussion

The solubilities of NaCl at 25° in different DMSO-H₂O mixtures are given in Table 1. Log *s* is plotted against the molefraction of water in Fig. 1. Solubility varies non-linearly with the molefraction of water. The plot of log *s* vs $x(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ was found to be composed of two straight lines meeting at $x(\text{H}_2\text{O})=0.675$. This indicates that the solubility follows two exponential laws: one in the molefraction range $x(\text{H}_2\text{O})=0-0.675$ and another in $x(\text{H}_2\text{O})=0.675-1.0$. The solubilities may be expressed by the relationships $S = A e^{bx}$ [$x(\text{H}_2\text{O}) = 0-0.675$] and $S = A' e^{b'x}$ [$x(\text{H}_2\text{O}) = 0.675-1.0$]. The values of *A* and *A'* are found to be $A=0.453$, $A'=0.08511$; $b=3.578$ and $b'=6.057$. The rate of increase of the slope is far greater in the mole

TABLE 1—SOLUBILITY OF NaCl IN DMSO-H₂O MIXTURES AT 25°C

Molefraction of H ₂ O	Solubility (g/100 g solvent mixture)
0.0	0.455
0.0119	0.4887
0.05	0.5727
0.1081	0.7297
0.2036	1.028
0.30	1.40
0.40	1.95
0.50	2.70
0.5985	3.96
0.701	6.70
0.800	10.99
0.8762	17.02
0.9428	25.21
0.9729	30.16

Fig. 1.

fraction region $x(\text{H}_2\text{O}) > 0.675$ than in the region $x < 0.675$. It has been reported⁵ that the solubilities in dipolar aprotic solvents are mainly determined by the solvation of anions. DMSO is a dipolar aprotic solvent and the solvation of cations takes place through the oxygen atom of the S-O dipole. Due to the inductive effect and the steric hindrance by the methyl groups, anion solvation is less in DMSO than in water. The low solubility of NaCl in DMSO supports this view.

Water is H-bonded whereas DMSO is not. It has been reported⁶ that the H_2O molecule in DMSO- H_2O mixture is more basic than in pure H_2O . This may cause an increase in the cation solvation. Even though the solubilities are lower in mixed solvents than those in pure water, there is a definite increase in solubility with increased mole percent of water even in the region $x(\text{H}_2\text{O}) < 0.675$. This indicates that anion solvation also increases with increasing mole fraction of water. It may be noted that cation solvation itself cannot cause an increase in solubility as is evidenced by the low solubility of the alkali-halides in DMSO. In the solvent mixture, unlike in pure DMSO, where anion solvation is less, more positive centres are available for anion solvation. It is reported that the solvation of Cl^- , Br^- and I^- ions is only slightly affected by the addition of water up to a composition DMSO- H_2O^4 . But we find that the solubility is more than six fold than in pure DMSO at this composition which indicates that considerable anion solvation takes place even before this composition

is reached. Literature shows that the solvent mixture with the composition $x(\text{H}_2\text{O}) \approx 0.67$ has peculiar properties⁵ compared to that of either DMSO or H_2O . The present work shows that there is an abrupt change in anion solvation above this molefraction as evidenced by the sudden increase in slope of the $\log s$ vs $x(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ curve. The change in value of A may be due to a sudden transition from a water modified DMSO structure to a DMSO modified water structure. Other structural studies like I.R., N.M.R. may shed more light on this point. We have calculated the solubilities in the various mixtures on the assumption that DMSO forms a definite hydrate of the composition DMSO- $2\text{H}_2\text{O}^7$. The experimental solubilities are found to be less than the theoretical values showing that no free water is available for solvation through the entire range. This leads us to infer that stoichiometry of the hydrates in the salt solutions is ill defined.

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